

MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES AND LEVEL OF USAGE OF SUPERLATIVE DEGREE OF ADJECTIVE IN THE TAJIK LITERARY LANGUAGE REFERRING TO 11TH CENTURY (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TARJUMAI TA`RIKHI YAMINI" BY JURFODIQONI)

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Abstract:

The given article dwells on the issues beset with morphological peculiarities and level of usage of superlative degree of adjective in the Tajik literary language referring to 11th century on the example of the historical production entitled as "Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini" by Jurfodiqoni. It is noted that in modern Tajik literary language comparative and superlative degrees are expressed in two ways: synthetic and analytical ones and the theme explored is of a long history and passed various periods and evolution throughout its development. Adducing the results of the analysis concerned with the theme explored one can come to the conclusion that in "Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini" by Jurfodiqoni, the superlative degree of adjective is evinced analytically. The relevant degree of adjective possesses certain common and distinctive peculiarities, on the whole.

Key words: adjective, superlative degree of adjective, morphological peculiarities, level of usage, Tajik language, expression of degrees of adjectives, suffix -тарин, "Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini" by Jurfodiqoni

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Introduction

It is common-knowledge that determination of various periods of the history of the language and its high points of development based on both scientific-historic traces and artistic ones we proceed from the assumption of the actual issues in the field of Tajik linguistics. Into the bargain, it is impossible to create commonly accepted standard grammar without dwelling on comprehensive analysis of artistic and scientific-historical legacy [1; 2; 3].

Language is a complex, multifaceted and developing system, which reflects all changes occurring in the society. At the modern stage of the development of linguistic studies, language is to be considered as an anthropocentric system, therefore, in the second half of the 20th century, the emergence of cognitive linguistics promoted the arrival of categories in science, which is an opportunity to study the relations between language and people`s culture. Every language has its own particular characteristics that make up various aspects, such as grammatical structure, word-stock composition and phonetic system. Each of the relevant aspects of language needs independent theoretical research. The grammatical aspect of the language was mostly paid attention to, but over time, other aspects including lexical, phonetic and other aspects of the language are also studied.

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Book review

While conducting analysis, we have resorted to “Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini” by Jurfodiqoni and we adduced the appropriate examples out of the above-mentioned source in order to bring certain thoughts and proofs. The chosen source depicts different historic events of Ghaznavids dynasty. This historical work is considered to be one of the priceless and fundamental historical sources contained a numerous historical facts and evidences belonging to the period in question.

The objective of the corpus of our study are:

- to dwell on morphological peculiarities and determine the level of usage of the suffix *-тарун* in terms of its function;
- to compare the relevance of the theme explored with modern Tajik literary language;
- to carry out certain distinctive features of superlative degree of adjective in the Tajik literary language referring to 11th century on the example of the historical production entitled as Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini” by Jurfodiqoni

Scientific novelty

The article under consideration dwells on morphological peculiarities and the level of usage of the superlative degree of adjective in the Tajik literary language referring to 11th century on the example of the historical writings [7] in Tajik linguistic studies, for the first time. It is worth stressing that the relevant grammatical degree of adjective in our factological materials is not an identical in terms of its usage and is of great importance in the exploration of this category of adjective.

Methodology

While canvassing the distinctive peculiarities and the frequency of uses of the suffix *-тарун*, we have resorted to the following visual methods, such as: comparative and historical, synchronic and diachronic ones.

Main results and dissuasion

As a rule, “the category of degrees of adjective is expressed by the suffixes *-тап* (comparative) and *-тарун* (superlative) in MTL. However, they differ from the current state with a number of peculiarities at various stages of the historical development of Tajik literary language, at the initial stage of the evolution of Dari-Tajik language, in particular” [1, p.58-64].

At the same time, in the Tajik literary language comparative and superlative degrees are expressed in two ways: synthetic and analytical ones.

Expression of Superlative Degree of Adjective

Basically, the frequency of the superlative degree of adjective by means of the suffix *-тарун* is the language of the historical writing belonging to the period under study. As a result of consideration, research and exploration of scientifico-historical traces of various periods, it became clear that the usage of the suffix *-тарун* is more limited than *-тап* historically. Into the bargain, this grammatical category of Tajik adjective is underscored a number of researchers. V.S. Rastorguyeva laid an emphasis upon the idea that “the grammatical category of Tajik adjective is characteristic of Tajik Literary Language and does not occur in dialects” [5, p.59].

While conducting an analysis concerned with the theme explored, we encountered that the suffix *-тарун* is used to perform this grammatical function in the following set of phrases: *сазовортарин* чизе [7, p.13], *шарифтарин* нафоис... *азизтарин* рағоиб [7, p.47], *меҳтарин* амир... *кеҳтарин* амир [7, p.180], *судмандтарин* сармоя [7, p.302], *охуртарин* авлод [7, p.317], *беҳтарини* он [7, p.337], *беҳтарини* ҳама [7, p.337], *беҳтарин* бахшоянда [7, p.340], *саргардонтарин* мардумакҳои чашм [7, p.340], *беҳтарин* мавқеъ [7, p.341],

беҳтарин ашхос [7, p.345], *беҳтарин* аҳвол [7, p.354], *беҳтарин* гиёҳон [7, p.370], *сутудатарин* ҷонишинон [7, p.352], *комилтарин* хушбахтӣ [7, p.354], *сахттарин* бало [7, p.357], *беҳтарин* чиз [7, p.358, 358], *сутудатарин* шахс [7, p.362], *бузургвортарини* эшон [7, p.365], *сахитарини* онон [7, p.365], *шоистатарин* касон [7, p.365], *беҳтарин* ҷомаҳо [7, p.369], *наздиктарин* хешу пайванд [7, p.374]: *Зишттарин* чизе, ки дар он рӯз ба чашм намоён мешавад, равшаниии риш аст, ки ба ҷомаҳои хизоб пӯшонидани шавад (сафедии риш олуи ба хизоб аст) [7, p.375].

a) Designing on the premise of our detailed observations, one important point can be underscored that in “Tarjumai Ta`rikhi Yamini” by Jurfodiqoni, traditionally, the superlative degree of adjective is formed by means of *-тарин* from the original Tajik ones: *сазовортарин* чизе [7, p.13], *меҳтарин* амир... *кеҳтарин* амир [7, p.180], *сахттарин* бало [7, p.357], *шоистатарин* касон [7, p.365], *наздиктарин* хешу пайванд [7, p.374]: Ва миёни мо *наздиктарин* хешу пайванд аст, агарчи насабе, ки моро ба якдигар бипайвандад, дур аст [7, p.374], Ман ёро *шоистатарин* касоне медонам, ки рӯи рег (хок) қадам гузоштаанд, барои виросату ҷойнишинии ашхоси бузургвор ва боманоату гушодарӯ ва сарварони некӯкору маъруф [7, p.365]

In reference to it, the word *беҳтарин*- *the best* is used more frequently in the corpus of our study: *беҳтарини* он [7, p.337], *беҳтарини* ҳама [7, p.337], *беҳтарин* бахшоянда [7, p.340], *беҳтарин* мавқеъ [7, p.341], *беҳтарин* ашхос [7, p.345], *беҳтарин* аҳвол [7, p.354], *беҳтарин* гиёҳон [7, p.370], *беҳтарин* чиз [7, p.358, 358], *беҳтарин* ҷомаҳо [7, p.369]: Ҳамагӣ *беҳтарин* ҷомаҳоятон (либоси сиёҳ)-ро ба худ баргардонед, ҳамоно пӯшидани либоси сиёҳ дар азои шахси фақид лозим аст [7, p.369].

b) Based on participle II verb+the suffix-a: *сутудатарин* ҷонишинон [7, p.352], *сутудатарин* шахс [7, p.362]: Халаф ибни Аҳмад *сутудатарин* ҷонишинон (ояндагон) аст ва бо сарварии худ бар аслоф бартарӣ пайдо кард [7, p.352], Қазову қадар бо тирҳои худ *сутудатарин* шахсро аз ҳайси дину мурувват ва фазл ҳалок кард [7, p.362].

c) As a rule, the expression of this degree of the relevant part of speech is performed based on the original Tajik derivative and compound adjectives: *судмандтарин* сармоя [7, p.302], *саргардонтарин* мардумакҳои чашм [7, p.340], *бузургвортарини* эшон [7, p.365]: Фазо тангтар аз он буд, ки рӯшноидиҳандааш (яъне хуршед) бад-он бирасад ва мардумакҳои чашми хуршед дар он макон *саргардонтарин* мардумакҳои чашм буд [7, p.340], Бибояд донист, ки суҳан шарифтар фазилате аст, ки одамӣ бад-он мутаҳаллӣ аст ва баландтар поест, ки фазли Офаридгор инсонро бад-он махсус мекунад ва бузургтар маосирест, ки оқил бад-он домани мафохир бар ашрофу ақобир мекашад ва *судмандтарин* сармояест, ки шарафи ахлоф баъд аз аслоф бад-он пайдо мешавад [7, p.302].

d) The superlative degree of adjective is formed by dint of a number of Arabic borrowed words: *шарифтарин* нафоис... *азизтарин* рағоиб [7, p.47], *охиртарин* авлод [7, p.317], *сахитарини* онон [7, p.365], *комилтарин* хушбахтӣ [7, p.354]: Дар *беҳтарин* аҳвол ва бо қадами муборак ва *комилтарин* хушбахтӣ, ки пайдорӣ ба дунболи он аст [7, p.354], Ва Шамсулмаолӣ дар икроми мақдам ва эҳтироми ҷониб ва иғтиноми мавриди ӯ ба ҳама ғояте расид ва мақдури хеш дар масолаху маночеҳи ӯ базл кард, то мулки қадим, ки *шарифтарин* нафоис аст ва *азизтарин* рағоиб, урзаи муҳиммот ва вақояи зоти ӯ кард [7, p.47].

Namely, both in MTL and in the earlier works, including: “Ta`rikhi Bayhaqi” (the 11th century) [6] and “Badoe-ul-waqoe” (the 16th century) [8] a number of set of phrases *аз ин*, *аз он*, *аз ту*, *аз худ*, *аз шумо*, *аз ҳама*, *аз вай* are resorted to in order to lay an emphasis on the comparative degree of adjective. As a rule, if the above-mentioned components come before the comparative degree, then they participate in the formation of superlative degree one that

is, “combination of the composition of *аз ҳама*, *аз тамоми* and the original adjective takes place analytically” [4, p.138]. If the above-mentioned compositions come before simple and comparative degrees, then they participate to express the superlative one and the author of this historical trace never used the relevant grammatical means and it is concerned to be one of the distinctive peculiarities of the theme explored.

Frequency of tusage of the suffix *-марун* in the language of in “Tarjumai Ta` rikhi Yamini” by Jurfodiqoni belonging to the 11th century based on the above-mentioned models

<i>Model</i>	<i>Times used</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
a	14 instances	58%
b	2 instances	8 %
c	3 instances	13 %
d	5 instances	21 %
Results	24 times used	

Conclusion

Adding the results of the analysis of the theme explored one can come to the conclusion that in the Tajik literary language of the 11th century, the superlative degree of adjective is evinced analytically and possesses certain common and distinctive peculiarities in terms of grammatical structure. The frequency of usage of the suffix *-марун* is not identical in the corpus of our study, in particular the relevant suffix is used 14 instances to form this grammatical category of adjective from Tajik original nouns, which equals 58 % more frequently and abundantly. It is worth stressing that comparative and superlative degrees are expressed in two ways in the Tajik literary language: synthetic and analytical ones and the theme explored has a long history and passed various periods and different evolution throughout its development.

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